

AN IMPROVED TEST SPECIMEN TO DETERMINE COMPOSITE COMPRESSION STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the design, development and application of a novel miniature sandwich test specimen to determine the compressive properties of advanced composites. The specimen consists of a core of neat resin sandwiched between identical symmetric laminate skins and generates composite compression strengths significantly higher than those reported to date. Failure modes are consistent and data variance is low. The unique specimen design allows testing in either axial compression or four-point flexure and precludes premature failure due to specimen buckling. Stress concentrations are also significantly reduced, thereby allowing for a better estimation of the material's intrinsic compression strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Of all the mechanical properties of composite materials, compression strength is perhaps the most difficult to measure. The root of this difficulty lies in the extreme sensitivity of the failure stress and failure mode to specimen and test variables. Axial compression testing of composite materials is predominantly accomplished by shear loading of the composite through bonded tabs. Failure in these tests frequently occurs at stress levels below the true compression strength, as a result of either global specimen buckling or stress concentrations in the gripped section of the specimen. The stress for the onset of global specimen buckling is influenced by the specimen quality (voids, fiber alignment, fiber distribution, variations in thickness, etc.) and the test procedure (specimen design and dimensions, test fixture, and alignment of the specimen and load axes). The stress concentrations (and hence the failure stress) in the gripped section of the specimen depend on the grip design as well as tab material, adhesive, thickness and taper.

Sufficient care in specimen preparation can ensure good alignment of the fibers with the specimen axis and a uniform total thickness of (flat and parallel) tabs and the corresponding adhesive layer. Most of the effort in refinement of the test procedure has centered on changes to the test fixture and specimen design. Some of this effort has been directed at modifications of the standard IITRI and Celanese test fixtures [1], specimen gage length [2] and tab material and design [3], and changes in the specimen design itself to include sandwich beams, tubes and rings in addition to rectangular coupons. Among more recent developments is a proposal to extract 0° compression strength from tests on crossply laminates [4]. Investigations of this method have revealed, however, that the calculated 0° strength is dependent on the ply stacking sequence [5]. The Group for Aeronautical Research and Technology in Europe (GARTEUR) has also introduced a modified Celanese test specimen in which nineteen 0° plies are laminated between eight $\pm 45^\circ$ plies on either side, and the specimen is waisted down to sixteen 0° plies in the gage section [6]. The use of such integral tabs spreads out the stiffness change from the coupon to the tab and promotes delamination at the tab/coupon boundary at low compressive loads, thus relieving the stress concentrations in the gripped region.

In addition to the specimen and test artefacts discussed above, constituent properties and ply stacking sequence also determine laminate compression strength. Constituent properties which may influence the failure stress are fiber stiffness and compressive strength, matrix shear modulus, interfacial bond strength, and fiber waviness (inherent in the prepreg, or induced during processing by a mismatch in coefficients of thermal expansion between fiber and matrix). When multidirectional laminates are subjected to compressive loading, interlaminar stresses at the free edges can initiate failure. For a given orientation of plies, the sequence in which they are stacked dictates the magnitude of these stresses and consequently the ultimate failure stress. There appear to be, therefore, a large number of variables which govern the failure stress of a composite material under axial compressive loading. A successful test method/ specimen should be able to minimize or eliminate the specimen and test artefacts to determine the true response of the material (not the structure) to compressive loading. In all attempts to improve the test method, success is generally measured by the magnitude of the increase in the failure stress. This implies that the intrinsic material property (for composites of high compressive strength) is still elusive. The true material property will be determined when the failure mode is independent of the specimen design, quality, or test fixture. The corresponding failure stress will depend only on the material properties under the test conditions and may be achieved *without the full compressive potential of the reinforcing fiber being realized*. To determine this failure stress, *independent of specimen and test variables*, is the challenge.

2. SANDWICH SPECIMEN DESIGN

Two of the major contributors to premature failure of composite specimens under axial compression are stress concentrations at the ends of the specimen gage section and bending (or global buckling) due to eccentric loading. An ideal specimen design should minimize (or eliminate) stress concentrations and allow the specimen to fail in compression before the critical buckling load is reached. A sandwich beam in which composite skins are separated by a material of lower modulus satisfies the latter requirement: the specimen fails at a lower load, since it has fewer composite plies than a conventional specimen, and the geometry provides greater stability against buckling. Sandwich specimens have been proposed before [7], and a four-point flexural test of a sandwich beam is incorporated in ASTM D-3410. This specimen is a rectangular beam with a unidirectional six-ply composite skin bonded to one face of a heavy density aluminum honeycomb core and an appropriate metal sheet bonded to the other face. The specimen is large (approximately 56 cm x 2.54 cm x 4 cm) and expensive to fabricate and has therefore seen limited use. In addition a mismatch in Poisson's expansions between composite skin and core causes premature debonding of the two under applied load. In spite of this drawback, the specimen yields a higher compression strength when compared to other specimen geometries.

To overcome the problems described above, the specimen size should be reduced to where it can be tested on conventional test fixtures in axial compression, material and fabrication costs should be reduced, and Poisson's ratios of core and skin should be better matched. With these criteria in mind a miniature symmetric sandwich specimen was designed with composite skins on *both* faces. The length and width of this specimen are the same as conventional (IITRI) test coupons, while the volume of composite is reduced by as much as 80 percent. The honeycomb core of the standard sandwich beam is replaced by a slab of neat resin (similar to the matrix of the composite to be tested), and skins and core are bonded *in situ* during composite processing, eliminating the need for an intermediate adhesive layer. Furthermore, Poisson's ratios of the resin core and unidirectional composite skins are better matched than in conventional sandwich specimens. Because of its unique design, specimens from the same panel can be tested in axial compression *and* four-point flexure. A sketch of the sandwich specimen is shown in Figure 1. The specimen geometry as well as the lower load required to initiate composite compressive failure should preclude global buckling as the initial failure mode, as has been verified experimentally.

Another key requirement to determine true compression strength is the minimization of stress concentrations in the specimen gage section. A finite element method was used to determine the stress distribution at the ends of the gage section for a sandwich specimen (with unidirectional two-ply skins) and the corresponding all-composite (24-ply) coupon. A four-noded quadrilateral isoparametric finite element mesh containing 1285 elements and 1378 nodes was employed [8], and the material properties used in the analysis are listed in Table 1. The out-of-plane stresses σ_z and τ_{xz} were found to be too small to influence the compressive strength. The stress distribution along the x-direction was

FIGURE 1. Geometry and dimensions of a miniature sandwich test specimen

determined for the outer surface of the skin (where it is maximum) from the center of the gage section. These results for the AS4/3501-6 composite system are shown in Figure 2. The maximum axial stress, σ_x , occurs at the end of the gage section for both specimen types, with stress concentration factors of 1.15 and 1.24 for the sandwich and all-composite specimen, respectively. These factors reduce to unity in both cases at about 1.5 mm from the end of the tab. These results were experimentally confirmed by determining the stress concentration factors using two strain gages (each 0.2 mm in length), one located at the center of the 12.7-mm gage section and the other near the end-tab. This sandwich design therefore has a lower stress concentration than the conventional test specimen and should provide a closer estimate to the intrinsic compression strength.

Parametric studies were also conducted to arrive at an optimum tab material and geometry [8]. A fiberglass/epoxy tab generates significantly lower stress concentrations compared to both aluminum and steel tabs and was therefore the only material considered in further studies. A reduction in the tab taper angle from 90° to 15° considerably reduces the stress concentration at the end of the gage section. The advantage gained in using small taper angles, however, is offset by the corresponding increase in the unsupported length between the grips and reduction of the critical buckling load. In fact, a majority of sandwich specimens with a standard gage length of 12.7 mm and a tab taper angle of 10° failed via buckling. There is a very slight reduction in the stress concentration factor with a decrease in tab thickness from 1.6 mm to 0.4 mm. In addition for a given taper angle, a thinner tab results in a smaller unsupported length. However, the tab should be thick enough to prevent any damage to the specimen as it is gripped and loaded. Different combinations of skin thicknesses (0.25 and 0.5 mm) and core thicknesses (3.2 and 4.8 mm) had a negligible influence on the stress concentrations. The results from these parametric studies are reflected in the specimen geometry depicted in Figure 1.

TABLE 1. Material Properties of Sandwich Specimen Components

Property	Composite Skin (AS4/3501-6)	Resin Core (3501-6)	End-Tab (Glass/Epoxy)
E_{xx} (GPa)	138	4.1	48.3
$E_{yy} = E_{zz}$ (GPa)	10.3	4.1	18.6
$G_{xy} = G_{xz}$ (GPa)	5.5	1.5	6.9
G_{yz} (GPa)	3.4	1.5	4.8
$\nu_{xy} = \nu_{xz}$	0.3	0.36	0.28
ν_{yz}	0.55	0.36	0.56
α_x (ppm/ $^\circ$ C)	-0.4	42	--
α_y (ppm/ $^\circ$ C)	15	42	--

A concern with a multilayered material such as this sandwich specimen is the generation of interlaminar stresses at the free edges under an applied load. Consequently, a stress analysis was conducted to calculate these interlaminar stresses for a sandwich with two-ply unidirectional AS4/3501-6 skins using a global-local model [9]. The largest interlaminar stresses, at an applied strain of 2.5 percent (which is the approximate failure strain of this material system), were found to be 17 MPa (normal) at the midplane of the core and 13 MPa (shear) at the skin/core interface. These stresses are not large enough to initiate interlaminar failure prior to ultimate failure of the composite skin in compression. This prediction is borne out experimentally by microscopic examination of specimens unloaded from close to the ultimate stress, which display no evidence of interlaminar failure. The close match of Poisson's ratios of skin and core are primarily responsible for these low interlaminar stresses. Similar results were obtained for carbon/PEEK and glass/epoxy composites.

3. SPECIMEN FABRICATION AND TESTING

The core of the miniature sandwich specimen is fabricated from neat polyetheretherketone (PEEK) or epoxy resins. For epoxy composites two different epoxy cores were employed: a 177°C-cure epoxy system (3501-6) from Hercules Inc. for unidirectional composites, and a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (Epon 828) from Shell Chemical Co. cured at room temperature with a polyamine hardener (Jeffamine D-230) from Texaco, Inc. for multidirectional laminates. The cores for PEEK composites were fabricated from 0.125-mm thick PEEK film (Stabar K) from ICI America, Inc. AS4/APC-2 composites as well as epoxy composites reinforced with PAN-based carbon, pitch-based carbon, E-glass, S-glass, boron and Kevlar filaments have been investigated with this specimen.

Sandwich panels of unidirectional epoxy composites were fabricated by co-curing skin and a partially-cured (or gelled) epoxy (3501-6) core with the recommended composite processing cycle. For multidirectional epoxy laminates, symmetric skins were first fabricated, and the Epon 828/D-230 resin system then cast between them and cured at room temperature to form the core. Thermoplastic sandwich panels were made by co-consolidating a stack of sheets of PEEK film between plies of AS4/APC-2 prepreg with the standard composite processing cycle. Details of sandwich fabrication are given elsewhere [10]. The number of plies in each skin varied from two to six for unidirectional composites and four to eight for multidirectional laminates. Epoxy cores were 3.18 mm thick, and PEEK cores varied in thickness from 3.0 to 4.4 mm. Simultaneous consolidation or cure of the components in a miniature sandwich panel eliminates the necessity of an intermediate adhesive layer while leading to excellent adhesion between skin and core. Compression test specimens were machined from these panels, and for comparison, all-composite panels were also fabricated and tested.

Specimens were tested in axial compression in an IITRI test fixture, with strain gages bonded to both faces of each specimen to monitor any bending or buckling resulting from eccentric loading. The compressive stress (σ_s) on the composite skin is calculated from the rule of mixtures:

$$\sigma_s = (\sigma_t - \sigma_c V_c) / V_s$$

where V is the volume fraction, and the subscripts t , s , and c refer to the total specimen, skin (composite), and core (resin), respectively. This expression assumes perfect skin-core bonding with uniform axial strain throughout the specimen. Identical axial strains in skin and core were verified by bonding an additional strain gage to the side of selected specimens. The expression above requires the stress in the core (σ_c) at the ultimate failure strain, and this is determined from compression tests on neat resin specimens. Both the neat resins (epoxy and PEEK) exhibit nonlinear stress-strain behavior

FIGURE 2. Stress concentrations on the surface of (2-ply) sandwich and (24-ply) composite specimens, in the gage section.

(Figure 3), and the data can be fit by quadratic expressions which are used to compute σ_c . The validity of the results obtained with this specimen was verified through tensile tests; calculated strengths and moduli were identical to those obtained with conventional composite coupons.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Compression of Unidirectional Composites

AS4/3501-6 is, by far, the composite system which has undergone the most extensive testing with this miniature sandwich specimen. Figure 4 shows two typical composite stress-strain curves from a specimen with unidirectional four-ply skins. This specimen was initially loaded to a strain of

FIGURE 3. Average compression stress-strain curves for neat PEEK and epoxy (3501-6) resins.

FIGURE 4. Stress-strain curves for the $[0]_4$ skin of an AS4/3501-6 sandwich specimen tested in axial compression.

1.5 percent, unloaded, and then loaded again to failure. Two features of note in this plot are the relatively high failure stress (in excess of 2000 MPa) and the significant departure from linear behavior. The nonlinear behavior is reversible (as seen from the overlap of the stress-strain curves for two successive loadings) and is attributed to a reversible reduction in fiber stiffness with increasing strain. These specimens failed predominantly in the gage section, with initial fracture of the composite skin at an angle of approximately 75° to the specimen axis (Figure 5A). This failure was accompanied by subsequent delamination and cracking in the core. Microscopic examination of the outer surface of the fractured composite skin revealed fiber cross sections with hackles (Figure 5B), all oriented the same way, suggesting a shearing of the fibers induced by the compressive load. On the same fracture

FIGURE 5. TOP: Composite fracture in the gage section of an AS4/3501-6 sandwich specimen; SIDE: Magnified view of the fracture surface near the outer surface of the skin.

surface but nearer the core, the fibers displayed distinct dual tensile and compressive fracture morphology with neutral axes all aligned in the same direction, features characteristic of fiber buckling. These observations suggest initial compressive failure on the outer surface of a skin, with the resultant eccentric loading promoting instantaneous buckling and global failure. Specimens with two-ply skins fractured in the same manner and at the similar ultimate stresses. With six-ply skins, however, failure was precipitated by global buckling, although at stresses significantly higher than obtained with all-composite coupons. IM8/3501-6 displayed a similar response to compressive loading as AS4/3501-6, with an average compressive strength of 2300 MPa (compared to 2070 MPa for AS4/3501-6). This result was unexpected, since in general an inverse correlation is observed between fiber stiffness and composite compressive strength for carbon fibers from the same precursor. (Moduli of AS4 and IM8 fibers are 225 GPa and 310 GPa, respectively.)

The compression strength of unidirectional AS4/APC-2 (ICI/Fiberite) is reported to be significantly lower than that of unidirectional AS4/3501-6, although both have the same reinforcement and matrices which display similar stress-strain behavior (see Figure 3). In axial compression, sandwich specimens with AS4/APC-2 skins failed at composite stresses lower than those obtained for AS4/3501-6 composite skins, although substantially greater than obtained with AS4/APC-2 (24-ply) all-composite coupons. Some specimens failed in the gage section with the skin fractured at approximately 75 degrees to the specimen axis. Under SEM examination the fibers on the fracture surface appeared to have a shear fracture morphology similar to that observed for AS4/3501-6 sandwich panels, while others displayed the dual tensile/compressive fracture morphology typical of fiber buckling. In other specimens the tabs debonded and the composite skin buckled at a number of locations below them. Our results (in Table 2) indicate that the difference in measured compressive strengths between AS4/3501-6 and AS4/APC-2 (normalized to the same fiber volume) is less than 15 percent. At least part of this difference may be attributed to the significantly higher residual stresses in the thermoplastic composite.

Because glass fibers have a lower stiffness than carbon fibers, the corresponding unidirectional composites are more prone to buckle under compressive loading, increasing the difficulty in determining this material's compression strength with existing test methods. Using the sandwich specimen, we investigated S-glass/1034 (Fiberite) and E-glass/1003 (3M) material systems. The

TABLE 2. Some Compression Strengths from Sandwich and All-Composite Coupons

Composite System	MINIATURE SANDWICH SPECIMEN				COMPOSITE COUPON	
	Skin Layup	Fiber Vol. (%)	Axial Loading (MPa)*	Flexural Loading (MPa)	Layup	Axial Loading (MPa)**
AS4/3501-6	0° (2,4 plies)	62	2070	1780	0 (20, 24 plies)	1400
	[0/90/90/0]		1080		[0/90]4S	805
	[0/60/-60]S		890		[(0/60/-60)S]4	685
	[0/45/90/-45]S		595		[(0/45/90/-45)S]4	645
AS4/APC-2	0° (2,4 plies)	57	1570	1630	0° (24 plies)	1100
IM8/3501-6	0° (2 plies)	62	2300		0° (24 plies)	1600
S-Glass/1034	0° (4 plies)	60	2280	1430	0° (24 plies)	1400
E-Glass/1003	0° (4 plies)	62	1223		0° (24 plies)	880
Boron/Epoxy	0° (2 plies)	50	3625		0°	2930

*Average strengths from 5-10 specimens, coeff. of variation <6%

**Average strengths (normalized to $V_f = 0.6$) from 5-10 specimens

composite skins of these specimens displayed linear stress-strain behavior in axial compression and failed catastrophically at stresses and strains substantially higher than reported in the technical literature. Failure occurred via a combination of fiber fracture, longitudinal splitting and delamination, with subsequent core cracking. In contrast, unidirectional all-composite coupons tested under similar conditions buckled globally at significantly lower strains. Representative composite stress-strain curves for both types of specimens are shown in Figure 6. The strain on each face of the specimen is plotted against the calculated stress, and a divergence prior to ultimate failure (Figure 6A) is indicative of buckling. This comparison illustrates the influence of specimen and test variables on the composite failure stress. It also clearly indicates the error in misrepresenting *any* failure stress under compressive loading as the composite compressive strength without first examining the specimen stress-strain behavior and failure mode.

FIGURE 6. Stress-strain curves for unidirectional S-glass/1034 composites tested in axial compression. LEFT: 24-ply coupon; RIGHT: 4-ply sandwich skin.

Some sandwich specimens were also tested in four-point flexure [10]. Thin rubber pads were placed between the loading pins and specimen to prevent premature local crushing of the skin, and strains were monitored on the faces in tension and compression. Epoxy composite specimens tested in this mode failed prematurely, initiated by cracking of the brittle epoxy core (presumably in that section subjected to tension.) This test was more successful with AS4/APC-2 sandwich specimens. Initial failure occurred in the gage section of the composite skin loaded in compression, via fracture at an angle of approximately 75° to the specimen axis, with accompanying delamination between the two skin plies. SEM examinations of the composite fracture surfaces revealed fiber shear as the primary failure mode with buckling of the delaminated surface ply at some distance from this failure site. Because PEEK is tougher and less sensitive to crack propagation than epoxy, the PEEK core did not fracture prematurely, and compressive strengths match those obtained from axial compression tests.

Composite compression strength is reported to be extremely sensitive to misalignment of the fibers with respect to the loading axis, with a misalignment of 1° causing a strength reduction greater than 50 percent [11]. Since in practice some misalignment is inevitable, even with the greatest of precautions, it was of interest to experimentally verify the results of this analysis using the sandwich specimen. Specimens were precisely sectioned from an epoxy sandwich panel with 4-ply AS4/3501-6 skins, with the *specimen* axis at angles of 0° , 2° and 3° to the *fiber* direction. These specimens were mounted in the test fixture taking care to ensure alignment of the *specimen* axis with the *loading* axis. Our test results indicate a drop in the average composite compression strength of 20 percent for a misalignment of 2° and a drop of 25 percent for a misalignment of 3° , compared to the strength for a 0° misalignment. While these reductions in strength are significant, they do not reflect the same sensitivity to fiber misalignment as suggested in the above analysis.

4.2 Compression of Multidirectional Laminates

Although it has long been recognized that current compression test methods are inadequate for unidirectional composites, they have been considered satisfactory for multidirectional laminates. With

the sandwich specimen we studied the compressive response of one cross-ply and two quasi-isotropic laminates of AS4/3501-6 [12]. Axial compression of cross-ply sandwich specimens (with [0/90]_S skins) gave an average laminate compression strength of 1080 MPa. By multiple loading of the same specimen to successively higher loads and microscopic examination between loadings, it was determined that initial failure occurred via fracture of the outer 0° ply and delamination from the neighboring 90° ply. In comparison, coupons from a 16-ply [0/90]_{4S} panel failed predominantly within the gage section at an average stress of only 805 MPa. In these laminates almost all the load is carried by the 0° plies. The 0° compression strength backed out from the 0/90 sandwich data is 2050 MPa (using a ply stress factor of 1.9 [5]). This is in excellent agreement with the average strength of 2070 MPa determined for the unidirectional composites with the sandwich specimen.

The compressive strength of a 32-ply [(0/45/90/-45)_S]₄ quasi-isotropic laminate was compared to that of eight-ply [0/45/90/-45]_S quasi-isotropic face sheets of a sandwich panel, and surprisingly, found to be marginally higher. The results of a failure analysis [13] suggested that in both specimen types initial failure occurred within the outer two plies in the following sequence: initial shear failure of the 45° ply, subsequent fracture of the outer 0° ply, and finally, delamination between the outer 0°, 45° and 90° plies. It appears, therefore, that in both cases failure occurred before the full compressive potential of the 0° plies could be realized. Compressive strengths were also compared for another quasi-isotropic configuration, with specimens from a 24-ply [(0/±60)_S]₄ panel and a sandwich panel with six-ply [0/±60]_S face sheets. In this case laminate compressive strengths from the sandwich specimens were 30 percent higher than those from all-laminate specimens. Initial failure in the former occurred within the outer plies and included surface ply fracture, splitting and delamination. Failure of the all-laminate coupons was more catastrophic, and the initial failure site could not be determined.

A stress analysis was conducted to calculate the interlaminar stresses at the free edges of these multidirectional laminate specimens to determine if they were sufficient to initiate delamination prior to compressive failure. The stresses at each layer of the cross-ply and [0/±60] quasi-isotropic laminates, at the ultimate failure strain, were found to be too small to induce interlaminar failure. For the [0/±45/90] quasi-isotropic laminate, however, the interlaminar shear stress (τ_{xz}) of the second layer (between the outermost 45° and 90° plies) exceeds the corresponding interlaminar shear strength (93 MPa) at the applied failure strain. The results of this analysis agree with the experimental observation of initial delamination at the outer 0/45 and 45/90 interfaces in the [0/±45/90] quasi-isotropic laminate. Delamination at the free edge could have triggered shear failure of the 45° ply with subsequent delaminations across the entire specimen. This would explain why sandwich specimens with [0/±60] quasi-isotropic skins demonstrated a higher compressive strength than those with [0/±45/90] quasi-isotropic skins.

4.3 Influence of Constituent Properties on Compression Strength

To determine the influence of matrix modulus on composite compression strength without changing other influential variables, tests were conducted on AS4/3501-6 and AS4/APC-2 sandwich specimens at a number of temperatures in the range of -85°C to 177°C [14]. Over this temperature range the matrix shear modulus (G_m), determined from compression tests on neat resin specimens, varies by at least a factor of two. In addition at any given temperature G_m also decreases significantly with applied strain. The composite compression strength (σ_c) is plotted in Figure 7 as a function of matrix shear modulus *at the failure strain of the composite*. From the plot the data for both composites clearly fall into two regimes; there is an increase in σ_c with increasing G_m up to a critical value (G_{mc}) above which σ_c is constant. To reach this plateau in compression strength requires $G_m > G_{mc}$ (at the test temperature), and especially for fibers of high compressive strength, a test free of experimental artefacts. Fractographic investigations of failed specimens revealed unmistakable evidence of fiber microbuckling at the higher test temperatures. It appears, therefore, that for composites of low matrix modulus failure occurs via microbuckling, with a direct correlation between the corresponding stress and matrix modulus. However, as the resin modulus increases beyond G_{mc} , the composite failure stress is governed by the compressive strength of the reinforcement. If the latter is true, then the considerable difference (approx. 500 MPa) in the maximum compression strength between the two composites reinforced by the same fiber requires an explanation. There are at least three factors which may contribute to this disparity, in different proportions: (1) lower fiber volume of AS4/APC-2 in this study (0.59 compared to 0.64 for AS4/3501-6); (2) higher residual compressive stresses in AS4/APC-2 due to its higher processing temperature; and (3) curvature or waviness of the fibers in AS4/APC-2 resulting from residual stresses which reduces the axial stress necessary for fiber shear failure.

FIGURE 7. Compression strength of AS4/3501-6 and AS4/APC-2 unidirectional composites as a function of matrix shear modulus.

There appear to be conflicting reports in the technical literature on the influence of the fiber-matrix interfacial bond strength on composite compression strength [15,16]. Investigations were therefore conducted with sandwich specimens on two epoxy composite systems: (1) AU4 (untreated) and AS4 (surface-treated) carbon fibers in 3501-6, and (2) (treated and surface-treated) T650-35 carbon fibers in ERLX 1901 (an epoxy with a cure cycle similar to 3501-6). Both AS4 and T650-35 fibers have similar moduli and tensile strengths. The test results, plotted in Figure 8, show a direct relationship between the interfacial bond strength (as represented by the composite 90° tensile strength) and longitudinal composite compression strength. A reduction in interfacial strength, besides possibly lowering the critical stress for microbuckling through a reduction of lateral support, can also alter the failure mode. AU4/3501-6 composites fractured predominantly in the gripped region and this was preceded by longitudinal splitting near the free edges. This failure may be precipitated by a combination of low interfacial bond strength and stress concentrations at this location. The T650-35/1901 specimens with an even weaker interface than AU4/3501-6 failed in the gage section, through delamination and subsequent buckling of the delaminated sections. The T650-35/1901 specimens with the strong interface failed in a manner similar to that described earlier for the AS4/3501-6 composite skins. The degree of interfacial bonding (no doubt in combination with other fiber and matrix properties) therefore appears to control the failure mode and the attendant failure stress under compressive loading. Further studies are required, however, to reveal the progression of failure modes and corresponding stresses between these two extremes in interfacial bond strength. Such studies will reveal if *for a given initial failure mode*, a change in interfacial bond strength has any influence on the measured compressive strength.

FIGURE 8. Compression strength of unidirectional (untreated and surface-treated) carbon fiber/epoxy composites as a function of 90° tensile strength.

5. SUMMARY

The miniature sandwich test specimen is simple and inexpensive to fabricate, requires a smaller volume of composite than an all-composite coupon, and can be tested with the same grips and fixtures used for conventional composite testing. With either unidirectional or multidirectional laminate skins, failure modes from carefully prepared specimens are consistent, and premature failure via global buckling or stress concentrations under the grips is eliminated. As a result measured composite compressive strengths are both reliable and reproducible, and consistently higher than those measured with conventional coupons. This specimen is invaluable in determining the influence of constituent properties on composite compression strength. The data reported here were obtained under precisely-controlled test conditions, and caution should be exercised in using these strengths to predict compressive failure in engineering composite structures.

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